

**CERTIFICATE
OF ACCEPTANCE**

This is to certify that the article authored by **Sotvoldiyeva Nafosat Qahramonjon qizi**, entitled “**Web-dasturlash fanini o‘qitishda muammoli yondashuvga asoslangan o‘qitish metodikasini ishlab chiqish**”, has been reviewed and officially accepted for publication in International Online Multidisciplinary Conference: Science, Education & Future Trends Bulletin.

The editorial board acknowledges the scientific value of the submitted work and confirms its inclusion in the forthcoming issue of the journal.

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